

ABSTRACT BOOK

#EHMA2022

EHMA 2022

**FROM PEOPLE TO SYSTEMS:
LEADERSHIP FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE**

**15-17 June 2022
Brussels, Belgium**

The EHMA 2022 Annual Conference

EHMA 2022 is the 27th Annual Conference of the European Health Management Association taking place in conjunction with the association's 40th anniversary. It brings together key healthcare stakeholders providing the latest evidence to guide the much-needed transformation of health systems. It supports managers and health systems to excel at a time where the complexity of the challenge ahead is immense.

The 2022 conference theme '*From people to systems: leadership for a sustainable future*' explores challenges and solutions to creating sustainable health systems and ways health managers can lead towards them.

One of EHMA's main areas of work has been maintaining a dialogue between policymakers, health managers and professionals, thereby facilitating policy refinement and change. The EHMA 2022 Annual Conference is an occasion for health managers and professionals to have their voices heard, to connect with decision-makers, and inform policymaking at the European level.

Every year, the EHMA Annual Conference attracts research from leading universities, creating space to exchange knowledge on excellent delivery of healthcare and showcase evidence-based practices at the country, systems and organisational level. The conference is abstract-driven and features research by leading experts on the most contemporary topics on health management. It is a place for all healthcare stakeholders to come together to exchange innovation and best practices.

The European Health Management Association

The European Health Management Association (EHMA) strives for excellent health management for a healthy Europe by supporting the spread of knowledge on effective health management practices. Active since 1982, EHMA exists so that Europe's citizens and communities can benefit from quality, safe, value-based care and health systems.

Our focus is on enhancing the capacity and capabilities of health management to deliver high-quality healthcare and support the successful implementation of health policy. Our commitment is on supporting the provision of data and research findings for evidence-based decision-making and monitoring health policies and practices.

EHMA is the only membership organisation in Europe to bring together the full health management ecosystem, including health and hospital managers, healthcare professionals, researchers, academia, policy and decision-makers. We are a recognised and respected amplifier of best practices in the evolution of health management, and we provide an environment where evidence, challenge and experience are valued and complex debates on current topics can take place.

135 - Health workforce for future: actions to strengthening the capacity of the health workforce in era of climate crisis

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Abstract

We are the witnesses of huge changes and health sector disorder due to COVID-19 pandemic crisis. Such real-life scenarios only showed us how fragile the health workforce is and how much action we need to undertake for any adaptation to future climate changes and related disruptions. For two years, the whole health workforce was in an emergency state. Burnouts, mental and physical pressure are everyday sights among health care workers and we only foresee the top of the iceberg. It is clear that we need preparedness for the crisis happening now and those to come. Building stronger health preparedness and climate-smart healthcare is essential. Preparedness for a chronic long term climate crisis we are already facing the consequences that need to come as a synergistic response to the COVID-19 and climate crises.

Health community supported global leaders at COP26 with a “Healthy climate prescription” and underlined, above all, the importance of strengthening health system capacity and resilience, leadership/governance and health workforce in climate change and health issues. COP26 was an opportunity to highlight the unique role of all health professionals and evaluate health system contributions to climate change, focusing on hospital carbon footprints, emissions reduction and insisting on consideration of both adaptation and mitigation strategies. It produced recommendations with the aim of improving the evidence-based policies to protect health from climate change.

WHO produced in 2020 guidance for climate resilient and environmentally sustainable healthcare facilities. This document aims to guide professionals working in healthcare settings to understand and effectively prepare for the additional health risks posed by climate change; monitor, anticipate, manage and adapt to the health risks associated with climate change. It is a guide for healthcare facility officials: to work with health-determining sectors (water and sanitation, energy, transportation, food, urban planning, environment), to prepare for additional health risks posed by climate change through a resilience approach, and to promote environmentally sustainable practices in providing these services. It provides tools to assist healthcare facility officials assess their resilience to climate change threats, and their environmental sustainability based upon the appropriate use of resources (water, energy, sustainable procurement), and release of hazards, to the surrounding environment. It is a roadmap for climate resilient and environmentally sustainable healthcare facilities, it promotes actions to ensure that healthcare facilities are constantly and increasingly strengthened and continue to be efficient and responsive to improve health and contribute to reducing inequities and vulnerability within their communities.

All these interventions require knowledge, skills and significant changes in the process of educating the health workforce for the future. Evaluation and advocating for increased climate change education for health professionals is essential. Intensifying changes in the process of educating the health workforce is a condition in shaping sustainable systems for achieving the goals for Climate-smart Health Care.

